

MEANING OF COLOR IN GUI DESIGN - COMPARISON OF ASIAN AND WESTERN
COLOR PREFERENCES

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Introduction

The corporate choice of color of products, logos, packaging, services, and other collateral is crucial in creating and sustaining a brand and the corporate image. Global presence companies have to consider the target country culture for international success despite globalism as an emerging factor. These companies have to customize their marketing strategy to fit the target country's cultural background. Similarly, companies with a global online presence have to pay close attention to this by customizing their website designs. This research paper looks into the color preference of Chinese and Western cultures and their usage in GUI.

Problem Background and Motivation

International integration between nations and societies is surging and affects business in the face of globalization (Callahan, 2005). Ultimately, well-established global products fail in emerging markets due to various reasons that can be categorized under the underdevelopment and insensitivity of companies to underdevelopment issues. These encompass insensitivity to

local cultures and the companies not being localized but instead stick to standardization. Another reason for the failure of the brands is the effects of the country of origin. Consumer goods fail since they are not locally manufactured, or they are not locally branded, packaged, and marketed. They are, in some cases, due to this effect, also not affordable as the pricing was done according to global standards, and this encourages home and handmade product circulation. Marginal successes are mostly recorded on non-consumer goods.

Therefore, several adjustments are needed for global brands to fit into consumers' needs and expectations in China and western countries. These adjustments need academic and industrial research conducted on customer cultural needs and expectations. High returns can be realized in the emerging markets by international investors if they look into these markets' cultural characteristics as they have varying effects on marketing. Markets influence the volatility of returns and trading volumes to varying degrees. Several economic, political, and even cultural characteristics should be factored in during marketing strategy, policy, and theory formulation from a well-informed investment decision making in the Chinese market. To this effect, products' marketing should be adapted to the respective countries to include their local environments and cultures. Emerging Asian market exhibit market heterogeneity characteristics. The Chinese economy has considerable variance on the product and service mean concerning those in other parts of the globe. The trend can be attributed to markets being majorly local, fragmented, low scaled, and served by small enterprises managed by the owners.

The Chinese market experiences large sociopolitical institution's influence. These institutions include religious, governmental, business groups, non-governmental, and local community formations (Rau, Plocher & Choong, 2012). These markets are more governed by institutions, therefore less competition, monopolies, and oligopolies. If marketing policies are

made in line with this factor, marketing can be more comfortable and cheaper. For the survival and prosperity of products in emerging economies, marketing strategies have to be rethought and reconstructed, and market function redefined.

There are both challenges and opportunities faced when companies join global markets. Using the SLEPT model to analyze these new markets is imperative to understand social, legal, cultural, economic, political, and technological environments' effects on marketing (Marcus & Gould, 2000). The model makes the challenges and opportunities encountered more depletive and helps companies save time and money. SLEPT factors have effects on marketing in economies. They encompass the challenges and opportunities companies face during their entry and operation in emerging markets.

Objectives

Theoretical Background

Customers on the landing page are directed by a series of channels where they can access products or services offered. The Graphical user interface enables the customer to communicate with a computer through the use of symbols, visual metaphors and pointing devices. In the face of cultural diversity and globalism, the user interface design becomes one of the most crucial areas to be carefully looked into in the creation of a web or mobile app (Kummer, Recker & Mendling, 2016). The color choice is an integral part of the main areas to be focused on an app or website GUI as it invokes particular visual or emotion to the users (Marcus, 2005). Apart from other aspects of design, color remains one of the most powerful bits in marketing in companies with global presence that reflects the brand personality. The correct choice of color helps attract and keeps customers as well as improve the communication of the company's message. Color serves to set basic mood, tone, concept and connotation for a product or brand. It is reported that

90% of online customers take around ninety seconds to assess the quality of an online product. Reports also claim that 75% of online product assessments made by people are subconsciously done and are influenced by color. The choice of the correct color for a company logo, packaging and brand with respect to host country cultures should be carried out based on research.

The UX color palette has been used by many companies with global business interest to improve user experience. The selection of the right color underpins better readability of information and increases the element strengths including call-to-call action. It has serves to enhance the navigation capabilities of customers and fulfill subconscious aesthetic user needs and stimulate intuitive interactions. The color of language, therefore, influences purchasing decision, making the color of UI design a central tenet in online marketing strategy.

The GUI can be divided into different elements including the content which include the headline and subheadline, unique value proposition, the GUI concept that encompasses sound, design and layout, the approach for information inclusion such as the newsletters, videos and images, images including promotional pictures and hero shot, trust building elements including protagonists and testimonials, pricing including offers and visual displays, footer and call to action encompassing terms and conditions, contacts, and privacy policy.

The graphical user interface is technically a tool that avails information of a product to a buyer. Its main objective is to attract and convince customers to buy a product. If the GUI succeeds in the objective, it is said that a conversion took place. The success of a graphical user interface is measured by the number of new visitors convinced to buy a product from a website. Improving the success of the GUI is, therefore, a continual process aimed at increasing the number of customers through GUI optimization. This process of attracting and successfully convincing a customer to buy a product from a website as influenced by the GUI is referred to as

the conversion funnel. The process of optimizing the rate of conversion is interactive and involves such steps as analysis, strategy testing, implementing, testing and realization.

Literature Review

Marcus and Gould (2010) investigated the general behavior of individuals of cultural dimensions in a thesis that looked into GUI elements rather than the design and posits that therefore is no direct connection between the design of GUIs and cultural color preference. On the other hand, Marcus (2003) identified several values making cultures comparable and posits that different cultures have different basic color preferences. The author concludes that people from different countries make different color choices.

Russo and Boor (2013) studied the general behavior of persons from different culture dimensions and found that there is a correlation between the value of people and color choices asserting that this correlation does not reduce with time and remain unchanged through decades. The author concludes that there is a strong correlation between GUI design color and customer preferences.

Marcus (2005) researched on the different types of websites and came up with information to help improve the configuration of the design in relation to different cultural dimensions. In a research that focused on the cultural design on website images, Rau, Plocher and Choong (2012) established a relationship between the color and cultures of different countries in product choice. The author focused his research on the cultural impacts of front-end design of software which is a desktop application and not a graphical user interface and found that the culture impacts the design of software.

From the literature review, it can be concluded that there is a correlation between culture and color preferences and therefore culture influences the choice of color in the design of

graphical user interface and computer applications. There is, however, a research gap. There is not study that focuses on the Chinese and western color preferences for General User Interface design, which this paper seeks to explore.

Cultural dimension

Cultural factors influence at least five components of graphical user interface, namely, metaphors, mental models, navigation, interaction and appearance. Metaphors as crucial components are conveyed through visual auditory or haptic cues used to characterize elements of the interface and interaction aspects. Mental models correspond to the organization of data, tasks, roles, functions and group members in such a way to reflect the content to be conveyed and can be understood easily by the user (Alexander, Thompson & Murray, 2017). Navigation is essentially the movement of mental models, for instance, the windows, panels and menu sequence to be encountered by the user. Interaction refers to the means used by users to communicate with a system, providing input and receiving feedback through it. GUI Appearance is made up of verbal, visual, tactile and acoustic perceptual display characteristics including the layout, aesthetic, icons, sounds, colors, orientation, language and verbal style.

Chinese GUI

Over the past decades, Chinese-specific user interface emerged to juxtapose to the Western HCI paradigm practices and standards. The Chinese user interfaces is made up of new metaphors, mental models, interaction paradigms, navigation schemas, and appearance elements fundamental to the Chinese culture and history. Chinese user interfaces take the form of ‘everything-in-one’ patterns also seen in voice messaging usage and the ‘cute’ mascot, animation and mascot popularity (Marcus, 2003).

Traditional Chinese values and color

The Chinese application model and coloring is dictated by the traditional Chinese values as opposed to the western style standards. Much functionality in Chinese GUI are designed to allow for reconfiguration, reinforcement and enhancement of the social practices based on the traditional Chinese values. The Chinese people establish and maintain social relationships through a development of persona and particularistic ties with other party (Plocher, Rau & Choong, 2012). Apart from the instrumental ties which are mostly temporary and goal oriented, such as the one witnessed between salesmen and customers, the color elements in Chinese GUI has to mirror a relationship with the culture and tradition beginning with identifying common grounds that can be reinforced through favor reciprocation. The moral obligation to the reciprocation of favors and observance of social norms is related to the Chinese social concepts of face, social prestige, and honor. These concepts are expected of every Chinese person, their relationship with the society and the design of products, including applications. When an individual or product fails to meet these obligations, they may lose the face, despite the Guanxi relationship developments that allowing the face to be saved or given to others.

The success of any application in the Chinese market lies in the integrated user experience as opposed to the western market concepts of quality and usability. The use of red color has been used by Chinese mobile money transfer applications as a digital version of the Chinese Lunar Year traditions, hong bao, a practice of exchanging monetary gift with family and friends based on Guanxi. Mobile and web application have different functions with different colors with each mirroring a relevant Chinese traditional practice. WeChat, for example, uses red colored packet function for money transfer to contacts (Marcus & Gould, 2010).

There are a range of differences in GUI that influence user preference and usage between the Chinese and Western groups. The Chinese, who are already familiar with western GUI,

express their preference for Chinese apps owing to the several unrelated functionalities embedded within a single application, each with meaning and relation to the Chinese culture. While most western app are not tradition and color sensitive, but are rather focused on product differentiation, the Chinese GUI design is sensitive to traditional practices and preferences. Most Chinese applications tend to have more functions than western ones and the color of each functionality is differentiated by cultural and tradition. On the other hand, western users are not color sensitive and access similar services through separate, task-specific apps.

Color and cultural differences

The Chinese and western cultures have a significant difference with regard to individualism and masculinity. The Chinese society is more collectivistic and characterized by building ties with other members of the society. The western social framework is loosely-knit and people tend to develop boundaries and take care of themselves only. The difference is also noted on masculinity as the Chinese society has a higher masculinity score with individuals are inclined towards the societal demand for competition and strive for success, whereas the western society does not value inclusion and standing out from the crowd. The Chinese society is also characterized by high Power Distance scores where people are influenced by authority and inequalities among people. On the other hand, communication in the western society has no hard-line stance as communication between one and her superior can be informal, participative and direct as opposed to the Chinese. There is also a difference in avoidance of uncertainty as the western cultures, such as the Dutch, show slight preference for uncertainty avoidance while the Chinese are comfortable with ambiguity and law and rule adherence and can be flexible with relation to the challenges. The western and Chinese cultures have strong long-term orientation, n that, they have a pragmatic nature and thriftiness to prosperity and endurance to achieve results.

All these affect color choice in Graphic User interface designs as each app differentiates its different functionalities depending on the role and relation to culture and societal values. It should also be noted that Chinese applications have more functionalities as opposed to the western applications which have relatively less functionalities as apps are more function specific (Russo & Boor, 2013).

The Asian and, more so, the Chinese culture is high-context and polychronic while the western culture, such as the North Eastern cultures including the Dutch, are monochronic and low context. The European thinking is comparatively more analytical and based on Cartesian logic in comparison to the eastern cultures whose thinking is more holistic and capable of considering logical opposites all together without conflict.

Chinese Collectivism, relationships

While most color choices in Chinese GUI design are based on culture and traditions and aimed a reinforcing social interaction, the western GUI design color choice is not as color sensitive. Both Chinese and Western app users find Chinese apps 'fun' and more convenient to use compared to the western apps despite the fact that western users are not much bothered by app and functionality colors. The Chinese culture associates good and bad image with color choices as they depict trust and societal judgment within the concept of keeping 'face'. The western culture is less concerned with color choice except for black which is more associated with poor reputation and mistrust.

Conclusion

The popularity of Chinese apps in china compared to the popularity of similar western apps in the country suggests that a successful GUI can only be derived from a specifically UCD process. Since the GUI design of Chinese apps is geared towards accommodating user needs

characterized by holistic pattern of thinking, polychromic attitude and high-context communication propensity, the GUI color choice as well as overall design strives to encompass the traditional Chinese values and allow users to build and maintain particularistic social ties and seeking common grounds. On the other hand, the western app UCD is characterized by analytical pattern of thinking, low-context communication propensity and monochromic attitude thereby providing task-oriented user interface which are less color sensitive to traditions as they are more focused on fast, direct service more suitable for individualistic, low context cultures.

Suggestions

The Chinese users prefer a holistic user experience design to task-oriented design focusing on usability and overlooks convenience. Due to this enamor for convenience in the Chinese app market, it is recommendable to incorporate different services and functionalities into one app differentiated by different colors in relation to corresponding Chinese tradition and culture. User experience in Chinese apps is enhanced by the consideration of traditional Chinese value aspects such as the Guanxi. Western app users are more lenient in attitude towards color choice as opposed to the Chinese app users. This means that Chinese GUI designers have to be more cautious to avoid losing 'face'. It is imperative to incorporate Chinese traditional color choices in GUI design.

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